

Microwave-assisted synthesis of Schiff's bases of 1,2,4-triazole derivatives and their anthelmintic activity

Biswa Mohan Sahoo^{a*}, K. Nagamounika^a and Bimal Krishna Banik^b

^aDepartment of Pharmacy, Vikas Group of Institutions, Nunna, Krishna District, Vijayawada-521 229, Andhra Pradesh, India

E-mail: drbiswamohansahoo@gmail.com

^bCommunity Health System of South Texas, Edinburg, Texas 78539, USA

E-mail: bimalbanik10@gmail.com

Manuscript received on line 26 September 2018, accepted 01 November 2018

Schiff's bases of 1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol are synthesized by multistep reactions. Schiff bases are the condensation products of primary amines with carbonyl compounds. These compounds possess imine or azomethine (-C=N-) functional group in their structure and are considered as a synthon to design and develop the various lead molecules. They exhibit various biological activities such as analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, anticancer, antitubercular, antioxidant, anthelmintic and anticonvulsant, etc. In the present study, benzohydrazide is used as the starting material. Benzohydrazide reacts with carbon disulphide and potassium hydroxide to produce potassium dithiocarbazinate. Potassium dithiocarbazinate undergoes cyclization in presence of hydrazine hydrate to yield 4-amino-5-phenyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol. Finally, Schiff's bases is synthesized by reaction of 4-amino-5-phenyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol with substituted benzaldehydes under microwave irradiations for 5–10 min. Microwave irradiation method has several advantages as compared to conventional heating method in terms of uniform heating, shorter reaction time, less byproduct formation and environmental friendly. The structures of all synthesized compounds were characterized and confirmed by FT-IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral studies with an objective to develop novel biologically active compounds. All the titled compounds were screened for their anthelmintic activity.

Keywords: 1,2,4-Triazole, Schiff's base, microwave, synthesis, spectral study, anthelmintic activity.

1. Introduction

Synthesis and development of novel and safe chemical entities of therapeutic applications have attracted many scientists in the field of pharmaceutical research. The nitrogen containing heterocyclic compounds are widely used as therapeutic agents. Among these, triazoles are most commonly found in clinically useful drugs¹. Triazoles are the 5-membered heterocyclic compounds with three nitrogen and two carbon atoms². With respect to position of the nitrogen atoms, the triazole ring exists in two isomeric forms such as 1,2,3-triazole and the 1,2,4-triazole as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Triazole ring and its two isomeric forms.

Out of these isomers, 1,2,4-triazoles are considered as more important pharmacologically active isomer³ as depicted in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Nomenclature and 3D structure of 1,2,4-triazoles.

The chemistry of 1,2,4-triazoles and their fused derivatives have been developed extensively and is still developing because of their synthetic and effective biological importance⁴. 1,2,4-Triazole derivatives possess various promis-

Fig. 3. Clinically useful drugs containing triazole moiety.

ing biological activities such as anti-bacterial, antifungal, antiviral, anti-cancer, anti-tubercular, diuretic, muscle relaxant, analgesic and anti-inflammatory, etc.⁵ as depicted in Fig. 3.

Based upon the medicinal activities of these compounds, we have synthesized six new Schiff's bases of 1,2,4-triazole derivatives using benzohydrazide as the starting material⁶⁻⁸. Benzohydrazide reacted with carbon disulphide in the presence of ethanolic potassium hydroxide solution and produced potassium dithiocarbazinate which underwent cyclization by reacting with hydrazine hydrate to produce 4-[amino]-5-phenyl-4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol. Further, various Schiff's bases were prepared by reacting 1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol with different substituted benzaldehydes under microwave irradiation method⁹⁻¹². The synthesized compounds were characterized by TLC, melting point determination and spectral studies by FT-IR, ¹H NMR and mass data. Finally, the characterized compounds were tested to investigate their anthelmintic activity.

2. Experimental

2.1. General:

New synthetic approach for a series of Schiff's bases of 1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol using benzohydrazide as the starting material is shown in Scheme 1. The starting material benzohydrazide (**1**) was obtained by esterification of benzoyl chloride with methanol in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid followed by the reaction with hydrazine hydrate. Benzohydrazide reacted with carbon disulphide in ethanolic potassium hydroxide solution to produce potassium dithiocarbazinate (**2**) which underwent cyclization by reacting with hydrazine hydrate to produce 4-[amino]-5-phenyl-4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (**3**). Further, various Schiff's bases (**4a-f**) were prepared by reacting 1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol with different substituted benzaldehydes under microwave irradiations for 5–10 min at power level-2 which correspond to 210 watt. The purity of synthetic compounds was determined by TLC. FT-IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral studies were carried out to characterize the structures of newly synthesized compounds.

Scheme 1. Synthetic route for Schiff base of 1,2,4-triazoles derivatives (**4a-f**).

2.2. Chemicals:

All reagents and solvents synthetic grade were purchased from S. D. Fine. Chem. Ltd., Mumbai, India. The synthesized products were recrystallized from ethanol as a solvent. Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes, expressed in °C and are uncorrected. The TLC analysis was carried out for checking completion of synthesis using 5×20 cm plate coated with silica gel GF-254. The purity of the compounds was checked by TLC using percolated silica gel-G plates and spots were observed by exposure to iodine vapors or by UV light. Chloroform and ethyl acetate were used as the solvent system or mobile phase. The compounds were characterized by using IR, ¹H NMR, mass spectra and elemental analysis. The IR spectra of the compounds were recorded on Shimadzu IR affinity using KBr discs and the values are expressed in cm⁻¹. The ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AC300 MHz spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard in DMSO-*d*₆. Elemental analyses of the newly synthesized compounds were carried out on Carlo Erba 1108 analyzer.

2.3. Synthesis of potassium dithiocarbazinate (**2**):

To the solution of potassium hydroxide (0.15 m, 8.5 g.) in ethanol (25 mL), benzohydrazide (**1**) (0.1 m, 1.36 g) and carbon disulphide (0.15 m, 14.5 mL) were added and the mixture was stirred for 1 h at room temperature. The comple-

tion of reaction was confirmed by monitoring TLC using silica gel-G. After completion of the reaction, the potassium salt of dithiocarbazinate (**2**) was obtained.

2.4. Synthesis of 4-[amino]-5-phenyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (**3**):

To the suspension of potassium salt of dithiocarbazinate (0.02 m, 4.44 g), hydrazine hydrate (0.04 m, 2 ml) was added and the mixture was stirred for 1 h at room temp. The color of the reaction mixture was changed to green color with evolution of H₂S gas. The completion of reaction was confirmed by monitoring TLC using silica gel-G. After completion of the reaction, ice cold water was added to get white precipitate and was acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid to get the final product (**3**). The product was filtered, washed with cold water and recrystallized from ethanol.

2.5. General procedure for the synthesis of Schiff's bases of 1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (**4a-f**):

To the solution of 4-amino-5-phenyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (0.001 m, 1.9 g) in ethanol (5 ml), different substituted benzaldehyde (0.001 m) was added. To this, few drops of the glacial acetic acid was added dropwise and the mixture was refluxed for 5–10 min under microwave radiation. The completion of reaction was confirmed by monitoring TLC using silica gel-G. After completion of the reaction, ice cold water was added to get the solid product of Schiff's bases of

1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (**4a-f**). The product was filtered, washed with cold water and recrystallized from ethanol.

2.6. Spectral data of Schiff's Bases of 1,2,4-triazole derivatives:

4-(Benzylideneamino)-5-phenyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (**4a**):

IR (ν , cm^{-1}): 3054 (Ar-CH. str), 2927 (Aliphatic-CH), 2438 (-SH), 1678 (N-N triazole), 1576 (C=N triazole ring), 1452 (C-N str); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ (ppm): 10.05 (s, 1H, N=CH), 7.44–7.86 (m, 9H, Ar-H), 2.56 (s, 1H, -SH).

4-(4-Fluorobenzylideneamino)-5-phenyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (**4b**):

IR (ν , cm^{-1}): 3055 (Ar-CH. str), 2928 (Aliphatic-CH), 2442 (-SH), 1680 (N-N triazole ring), 1579 (C=N triazole ring), 1450 (C-N), 1400–1000 (C-F str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ (ppm): 10.08 (s, 1H, N=CH), 7.48–7.84 (m, 9H, Ar-H), 2.63 (s, 1H, -SH).

2-((3-Mercapto-5-phenyl-4H-1,2,4-triazol-4-ylimino)methyl)phenol (**4c**):

IR (ν , cm^{-1}): 3056 (Ar-OH), 2925 (Ar-CH), 2856 (Aliphatic-CH str), 2441 (SH), 1605 (C=N triazole ring), 1577 (C=N triazole ring), 4151 (C-N); MS, m/z (%): Found for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$: 296.35.

4-(4-(Dimethylamino)benzylideneamino)-5-phenyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (**4d**):

IR (ν , cm^{-1}): 3316 (N=CH str), 2912 (Ar-CH), 2817 (Ali-

phatic-CH), 2557 (SH), 1666 (N-N str), 1601 (C=N), 1437 (C-N).

4-(4-Nitrobenzylideneamino)-5-phenyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (**4e**):

IR (ν , cm^{-1}): 2924 (Ar-CH), 2734 (-SH), 1707 (N-N triazole ring), 1605 (C=N triazole ring), 1536 (Ar- NO_2), 1381 (C-N triazole ring); MS, m/z (%): Found for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_5\text{O}_2\text{S}$: 325.35.

4-(4-Chlorobenzylideneamino)-5-phenyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (**4f**):

IR (ν , cm^{-1}): 2946 (Ar-CH), 2841 (Aliphatic-CH), 2557 (SH), 1685 (N-N triazole ring), 1585 (C=N triazole ring), 1418 (C-N), 710 (C-Cl str); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) δ (ppm): 10.01 (s, 1H, N=CH), 7.47–7.96 (m, 9H, Ar-H), 2.51 (s, 1H, -SH).

3. Biological evaluation

3.1. Anthelmintic activity:

Indian adult earthworms of the genus and species, *Pheritima posthuma* were used to study the anthelmintic activity. The earthworms were collected from the water logged areas of soils in Nunna, Andhra Pradesh, India were washed with normal saline to remove all the fecal matter and waste surrounding their body. The earth worms (*Pheritima posthuma*) 5–8 cm in length and 0.2–0.3 cm width weighing 0.8–3.04 g were used for all experiment protocols. The earthworms resembled the intestinal roundworm parasites of human beings both anatomically and physiologically and hence were used to study the anthelmintic activity^{13–15}.

Table 1. Characteristics and yield of synthesized compounds (**4a-f**)

Compd. code	Molecular formula	X	M.W. (g/mol)	Color	R_f value	m.p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Yield (%)
4a	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{S}$	H	280.35	Gray	0.55	198–200	72
4b	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$	-F	292.36	Brown	0.63	290–293	66
4c	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$	-2OH	296.35	Pale-green	0.62	261–269	64
4d	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_5\text{S}$	$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{-NH}$	323.42	Pale-yellow	0.65	240–249	72
4e	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_5\text{O}_2\text{S}$	- NO_2	325.35	Deep-yellow	0.64	165–168	81
4f	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClN}_4\text{S}$	-Cl	314.79	White	0.61	210–219	68

Procedure:

Gum acacia solution (1%) was prepared in normal saline. Test solutions were prepared by using this solution. Sample were taken petriplates and adult healthy earthworms ($n = 6$) were introduced in to them. Observations were made for the time taken to paralyze and time taken for death of the organism. Paralysis was said to occur when the worms do not review even in normal saline. Death was concluded when worms lost their motility followed by fading away of the body colour, and the values are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Anthelmintic activity of Schiff's bases of 1,2,4-triazole derivatives (**4a-f**)

Sl. No.	Treatment groups	Dose (mg/ml)	Paralysis time	Death time
			in min	in min
			Mean±S.E.M	Mean±S.E.M
1.	4a	100	27±0.52	30±0.2
2.	4b	100	31±0.765	35±0.57
3.	4c	100	25±1.3	30±0.416
4.	4d	100	20±1.5	23±0.581
5.	4e	100	22±0.36	24±0.556
6.	4f	100	30±0.962	33±0.581
7.	Control	Normal saline	–	–
8.	Albendazole (Standard)	100	18±1.1	22±2.5

4. Results and discussion**4.1. Chemical synthesis:**

Various Schiff base of 1,2,4-triazole derivatives were synthesized by reaction of 4-amino-5-phenyl-4*H*-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol with different substituted benzaldehydes. The yield of final product obtained was 64–81% by using microwave irradiation technology. All the synthesized compounds were soluble in methanol and dimethyl sulphoxide and insoluble in water, ethanol and benzene. Table 1 shows the molecular formula, molecular weight, melting point, percentage yield, R_f value and color of all synthesized compounds. The solvents chloroform and ethyl acetate (60:40) are used as mobile phase for monitoring TLC. The spectra of show usually a peak, near 1625–1650 cm^{-1} , characteristic of α,β unsaturated carbonyl group. The α -H and β -H of triazoles resonate at in the ^1H NMR spectra. The IR spectrum of 1,2,4-triazole derivatives (**4a-f**) showed absorption at λ_{max} at 2924–3316 cm^{-1} (aromatic-CH), 1536 cm^{-1} (aromatic nitro), 1585–1601 cm^{-1} (C=N str), 2241–2734 cm^{-1} (triazole -SH str), 3056 cm^{-1} (aromatic-O-H). In the ^1H NMR spectrum, the aromatic

Fig. 4. Anthelmintic activity (paralysis time) of Schiff's bases of 1,2,4-triazole derivatives.

protons were observed as a singlet δ 2.51–4.99 cm^{-1} (s, 1H, OH and 1H, -SH) the proton of the =CH and =NH of 1,2,4-triazole nucleus resonated as a sharp singlet at δ 8.92 and 10.01 respectively. The aromatic protons were seen as a multiplet at δ 6.86–8.56. (m, 9H, Ar-H). The mass spectra of the 1,2,4-triazole derivative were showed molecular ion peak corresponding to their molecular formula. Compound **4c** and **4e** showed molecular ion peak at m/z 296.35 and 325.35 respectively.

Fig. 5. Anthelmintic activity (death time) of Schiff's bases of 1,2,4-triazole derivatives.**4.2. Anthelmintic activity:**

Among all the newly synthesized 1,2,4-triazole derivatives, some of the selected compounds were evaluated for anthelmintic activity at the concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and the results were compared with standard drug Albendazole. Among the evaluated compounds, compound **4d**, **4e** and **4c** showed significant activity as compared to standard drug (Albendazole). The order of anthelmintic activity of synthesized compounds against *Pheritima posthumais* **4d** > **4e** > **4c** > **4a** > **4f** > **4b**.

5. Conclusion

In this work, our aim is to optimize the purity and yield of product, reaction time, eco-friendly reaction by the help of

microwave-assisted organic synthesis. The anthelmintic activity of titled compounds were performed at the concentration of 100 µg/ml and the results of evaluation study indicates that compounds **4c**, **4d** and **4e** exhibited significant activity as compared to standard drug. Hence, it can be concluded that, this new class of compounds certainly holds a greater promise in designing potent anthelmintic agents.

Abbreviations

Cl: Chloro, °C: Degrees Celsius, F: Fluoro, h: Hour, IR: Infrared, KBr: Potassium bromide, MF: Molecular formula, mg: Milligram, ml: Milliliters, MHz: Megahertz, MWI: Microwave irradiation, NO₂: Nitro, nm: Nanometre, NMR: Nuclear magnetic resonance, OH: Hydroxy, ppm: Parts per million, % : Percent, S.E.M.: Standard Error Mean, TLC: Thin layer chromatography, TMS: Tetramethylsilane, W: Watt.

Acknowledgements

The authors are thankful to Vikas College of Pharmacy, Vissanapeta, Andhra Pradesh, India for providing necessary facilities to carry out the research activities.

References

1. A. Mobinkhaleedi, N. Foroughifar, M. Khanpour and S. Ebrahimi, *Eur. J. Chem.*, 2010, **1**, 33.
2. B. P. Singh, *Int. J. Pharm. Res. and Dev.*, 2011, **4**, 51.
3. A. Hasan, A. A. Ameer, A. Ahmed and E. Yousif, *J. Chem. Pharm. Res.*, 2015, **7**, 531.
4. N. Karaalia, E. Mentesea and Y. Fatih, *S. Afr. J. Chem.*, 2013, **66**, 72.
5. N. Demirbas, S. A. Karaoglu, A. Demirbas and K. Sancak, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2004, **39**, 793.
6. A. J. Atia, *Molecules*, 2009, **14**, 2431.
7. P. K. Sahoo, R. Sharma and P. Pattanayak, *Med. Chem. Res.*, 2010, **19**, 127.
8. T. Coban, B. Can-Eke, S. Ozbey and M. Iscan, *J. Enz. Inhib. Med. Chem.*, 2005, **20**, 503.
9. E. Bheemappa, Y. D. Bodke, P. S. Krishnegowda, S. P. Venkata and R. Ningegowda, *Arch. Pharm.*, 2013, **346**, 922.
10. D. S. Dayama, P. N. Khatale, S. A. Khedkar, S. R. Nazarkar and P. A. Vedpathak, *Pharm. Chem.*, 2014, **6(5)**, 123.
11. P. P. Munj, R. R. Somani and A. V. Chavan, *Pharm. Chem.*, 2010, **2(1)**, 98.
12. R. Agrawal and S. S. Pancholi, *Der Pharm. Chem.*, 2011, **3(6)**, 32.
13. I. Khan, S. Ali, S. Hameed, N. H. Rama, M. T. Hussain and A. Wadood, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2010, **45**, 5200.
14. N. R. M. Gabr, *Asian J. Pharm. Anal and Med. Chem.*, 2015, **3(2)**, 62.
15. X. X. Ye, Z. F. Chen, A. J. Zhang and L. X. Zhang, *Molecules*, 2007, **12**, 1202.